

Impact of Occupational Stress on Job Performance: Moderating Role of Social and Supervisor's Support

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Abstract:

We use a regression analysis model to inspect a moderating effect of social and supervisor support on occupational stress and job performance. Our sample is based on 251 employees of different organizations. Data congregation approach is based on adoptive survey technique. Our results recommend that there is a strong impact of moderators on occupational stress and job performance.

Keywords: Regression Analysis, Social and supervisor support, Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational stress is considered one of the major problems in the organizational structure as it has a direct link with the performance of an employee that in turns affect the overall performance of that particular firm/organization. Stress in terms of employee can be in any form like accidents, unsatisfactory job or any kind of illness (Davidson & Cooper, 1981). Job stress and stress related job issues and then its impact on the performance were raised in 1978 by Bheer.

Recently occupational stress has been renamed as 'Psychosocial Hazard' by some of the researchers and linked it in the occupational risk management (McMichael, 1979). This work of McMichael was then further elaborated by Colin D. Butler, to find the major challenges coped with the occupational stress. He considered the physical health issues in relation to the mental stress from job of an employee. Under the condition of the working hours, physical and mental health disorders are being caused by the stress of the work under a particular organization that provides such a stressful environment to the workers (Colin D. Butler, 2015).

On the same stream of line, another research on the physiological health issues in relation to the occupational stress was done by James A. Wells et al. in this research they tried to find out the relation of occupational stress and physical health in association with 12 major measures of the prevailing stress at work and its association with five common health issues. They reached on the analysis that occupational stress has a wide effect on the health of the workers (James A. wells, 2016).

A qualitative analytical approach was used by Jacky Boivin et al. to study and analyze that the stress issues are not only limited to the corporate sector but it is widely spread in each area of work. Those who are providers of health are also suffering with this disease – hospital workers. They had taken the case of the workers who works in the fertility clinic and measure their level of work stress and the impact of that stress on their health. Their results show that fertility clinic staff perceives numerous work-Stressor and sources of difficulties with patients (Jacky Boivin, 2017).

Another remarkable work had been done by Faith Gibson et al. where he reports the analysis of the occupational stress in the social society. In this research they took the large data sample of social worker in Northern Ireland fields. Study formulated a wide part of inter-professional linkage of social workers (Teacher & Nurses). It was found that the stress in their personal life is much less than the stress they are getting from their jobs (Faith Gibson et al., 2017).

The question one might can think that, is this job stress is limited to the occupational employees or the person who are self-employed can be the target of this problem. To answer this question Jolanda Hessel by using Job Demand Control Model 'JDC'. According to this model the increasing demand of the job can increase the stress of the job and if the control factors are employed with the job then this stress can be reduce. Their findings

ended on the analysis that show that self-employed individuals with employees experience more work-related stress than those without employees because of higher job demand (Jolanda et al., 2015).

An encouraging work surrounding is characterized by employee perceptions that co-workers are fully concerned about their role and that supervisor's sponsor and assist employees' effort (Moos, 1981). Encouraging occupational environments are normally linked with enhanced work-place attitudes and added fruitful behaviors (Day and Bedeian, 1991). Distinctively, criticism indicates that a compassionate workplace reduces job pressure and its pessimistic effects (Schaubroeck, Cotton and Jennings, 1988).

Organizational support theory suggest that human resources represent universal imitation of the level to which the organization provides sufficient resources and values them as persons, as well as the possibility that the organization will compensate their work and facilitate them in hard times (e.g., during organizational change; Eisenberger et al. 1986; Shore and Shore 1995; Rhoades and Eisenberger 2002). The improvement of a helpful idea about the support employees get from the organization will guide towards the encouraging results for both the organization and the employees.

Regardless of the well-documented association among work stressors and strains (Beehr, 1985; House 1981; Fisher & Gitelson, 1983; Jackson & Schuler, 1985), the perceptiveness of the dominant variables in the course through which job stressors influence strains is restricted (Beehr, 1994; Folkman, 1981; Kinicki, McKee, & Wade, 1996). One of the variables consideration to moderate during this practice is social support (e.g., Ganster, Fusilier, & Mayes, 1986; Turner, Frankel, & Levin, 1983; Vaux, 1988). Social support has been defined generally as "the availability of helping relationships and the action of those relationships" (Leavy, 1983, p.5).

When workforce identifies strong organizational support, their socio-emotional requirements are considered to be fulfilled and they are expected to have additional constructive work attitudes, together with job satisfaction. On the other hand, if employees do not experience supported by the organization they may refuse to give effort (consequentially poor levels of performance) and report more negative job attitudes. A strong positive relationship was exposed by the meta-analysis of Rhoades and Eisenberger (2002) between organizational support, job satisfaction and job performance. We reproduce these outcomes and suggest in our existing model that employees' who observe higher levels of organizational and Supervisor's support will also describe higher levels of job satisfaction and will reveal higher levels of performance. In the following sections we describe the moderating role of supervisor's support and Social support in the relationships occupational stress and job performance.

The moderating effects of social support have formed different results. While several studies have establish moderating effects (e.g., Abdul-Halim, 1982), others have not (e.g., Ganster et al., 1986) or have originate support for an opposite moderating effect (e.g., Kaufmann & Beehr, 1986). An inverse moderating effect is experienced with the relationship of stress and performance.

Prospective moderators of these relations were weak, suggesting the subsistence of four common constructs of stress, job performance, social support and supervisor's support. A range of models for social support and Supervisor's support for occupational stress were examined for this general constructs. Consequences shows that social and supervisor's support had an effect on occupational stress – job performance relations. Social and supervisor's support concentrated the stress faced, mitigated supposed stress, and moderated the occupational stress – job performance association. Moreover, the disagreement that social support is mobilized when stressors are faced was not reliable with the available observed facts. A comparable need of support was set up to influence that support is require when stressors are faced and that support is provided when persons are affected with stress.

Theoretical Background and Research Hypothesis

Occupational Stress

Job or occupational stress is not only restricted to the men but also striking poorly the women as well. In this contemporary world, we are meeting with many operation associated to the participation of Women in the managerial and supervisory posts. This is the most emerging issue in developing countries. In the struggle of getting the administrative position in the organizations, women also have to face the stress issues. Study has been conducted by Gourie Suraj –Narayan, in which he proceeds that at which intensity women on the administrative posts are getting stress. He consider the sample of 30 women on administrative positions with different background and conclude that the stress effects the women on all levels of the managerial positions, the conservation approach to stress handling through multidimensional framework was mainly suitable (Gourie, 2017).

Stress can come from any situation that makes you feel upset, irritated, or uneasy. Everyone takes circumstances in different ways and has diverse coping style. For this cause, no two people will counter closely in the same mode to a particular state of affair.

Occupational Stress and Job Performance

Occupational stress is considered as a great distress to employees of the organizations. Researchers are of the same opinion that stress is a severe issue in many organizations (Cooper and Cartwright, 1994; Varca, 1999; Ornelas and Kleiner 2003). The occupational stress cost heavily for many organizations in current era. For example, the International Labour Organisation (ILO) reports that occupational inefficiencies may cost up to 10% of a country's GNP (Midgley, 1996).

Occupational stress is also caused by short of resources and equipment; work routine (e.g. overtime) and organizational environment are considered as major contributors to employees stress. Occupational stress result high frustration among the employees, low job performance, suffers exhaustion and ineffectual interpersonal relations (Manshor, Rodrigue, and Chong, 2003). Johnson (2001) also argued that identifying the signs of stress, the probable effects of such signs and establishing possible projected solutions for such signs are mandatory.

On the basis of such discussions and studies we have develop our hypothesis that the stress faced by the organization have a significant negative impact on the performance of the employees.

H1: Occupational Stress will have a negative significant effect on job performance.

Social Support and Job Performance

Social support is commonly identified and sound studied. There are a number of ways to define social support. Therefore, it is difficult to recognize just one. Still, the subsequent important basics are frequent in most definitions: social support “..may be regarded as resources provided by others, as coping assistance, as an exchange of resources, or even as a personality trait”. Distinct from social integration, which describes the quantitative way to show a person’s social relationships; social support also characterizes the qualitative aspects of interaction. Researchers have the same opinion that giving and getting social support is an effective method and should be taken under the perception of reciprocity, refers to give support that is certainly related with getting it.

Social support is a common, day after day fact. In general, most of the people found socially supported in their lives, moreover, at the workplace. 5th European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS) in 2010 reported 73% respondent felt supported by the peers and colleagues and 63% by the managers. Though, it is significant to remind that this information is simply delegate European context. For instance, the First Korean Working Conditions Survey in 2005 showed only 29% of South Korean being supported by their peers and colleagues.

On the basis of the past studies, we construct a hypothesis for our study and suppose that the social support positively effect and impact on job performance. In other words we can say that the person who are supported socially perform well in their professional career.

H2: Social Support will have a positive significant effect on job performance.

Supervisor’s Support and Job Performance

Supervisors are primary stage of administration where they specified with key responsibilities to shape and direct employees in organizations (Elangovan & Karakowsky, 1999; Goldstein & Ford, 2002; Noe 2008). They take part in a vital position as an mediator between administration and operational workers. As an organizer, difficulty handler and role model, supervisors frequently work along with their workers to plan, execute and observe the managerial policies, measures and strategy, as well as instructing programs (Comstock, 1994; Robbins & DeCenzo, 2004; Ellinger et al., 2005).

The supervisor’s responsibility in guidance programs is repeatedly considered as a significant organizational environment element where it can manipulate the efficiency of guidance programs (Noe, 1986, 2008; Blanchard & Thackers, 2007). Many scholars like Facticeau et al. (1995), Chiaburu and Tekleab (2005), and Ismail et al. (2007) analyse that supervisor’s position in such instructional areas has two significant qualities: communication and support. Support is mostly associated with supervisor who encourages and provide opportunities for improvement of employees performance at work place (MacNeil, 2004; Noe, 2005). In an instructional circumstances, supervisors encourage and inspire trainees to participate in such training programs, assist them throughout the programs regarding time, budget assistance and resources. Supervisor may also participate in vital roles for taking effective decisions with the participation of employees, and lead them about the new ways to achieve organizational targets. (Elangovan & Karakowsky, 1999; Nijman, 2004; Tai, 2006).

In the light of above discussions we consider that supervisor support have a significant positive effect on job performance. The employees who get support from their supervisors perform well in achieving organizational objectives.

H3: Supervisor’s support will have a positive significant effect on job performance.

Moderating role of Social Support between Occupational Stress and Job Performance

The moderating hypothesis (e.g., Kirmeyer & Dougherty, 1988; LaRocco, House, & French, 1980) states that social support interacts with stressors to affect strains; specifically, the relationship between stressor and strain is thought to be stronger for those individuals with low levels of support. To test for moderator effects, the most widely used data-analytic strategy involves examining the increase in R² when the interaction term (the cross-

product of stressors and support) is added to the regression equation of strain on the main effects of stressors and support.

According to the previous discussions and finding we consider social support have a moderating effect on the stress and job performance relationship. Considering that the employees who are socially supported can cope up with the stress more easily and effectively perform their organizational obligations.

H4: Social support will moderate the relationship between occupational stress and job performance in a way that this negative relationship will be weaker.

Moderating role of Supervisor's Support between Occupational Stress and Job Performance

Supervisor's role is measured as suggesting and assessing organizational customs for effective dealing with workers that demonstrate how manager gives importance to the employees in effectively performing their duties. The organizational support theory explains that if an employee receives high level support from the organization, his output will improve (Eisenberger et al., 2001). According to Eisenberger et al., (1986) there is a trend to believe among employees that they are being valued by the organization if they receive some level of organizational support. It has already been accepted with a number of studies that organizational support is related with the job performance; make supportive surroundings among peers, establishing and contributing new ideas for the improvement of organization, and completion of organizational responsibility (Eisenberger et al., 1990; Shore & Wayne, 1993). From above debate it can be accomplished that more supervisor's support leads towards added devoted approach toward performance of the organizational duties, in contrast to the employees do not supported by the organization.

Under the organizational support theory, we consider supervisor's support as a moderator of our study, having an effect that such support can reduce the stress of the organization and work and will help the employees in improving their performance.

H5: Supervisor's support will moderate the relationship between occupational stress and job performance in a way that this negative relationship will be weaker.

Research methodology

Sample and Data Collection Procedures

Data for this study was collected from employees of different service sector private organizations. The sector was considered to be useful for the study because they have to be more alert and vigilant regarding the completion of their tasks, are unsecure regarding their jobs, stressed by more efficiently producing the effective results. Convenience sampling technique was used to collect data. Self-administered survey questionnaire method was used for the collection of data. A cover letter was attached with the questionnaire which explains the purpose of the study to the respondent. Confidentiality and unanimity was ensured to the respondents. The participation was voluntary.

A total of 300 questionnaires were distributed. 268 questionnaires were returned out of which 17 were un-useable due to incomplete or multiple answers of the same question. Overall response rate was 83.6% on the basis of total useable questionnaires. 65.1% of the respondents were male and the remaining 33.3% were females. Average age of the respondents was between 25-54 years. Major of the respondents were between the age of 25-34 years accumulating 53.3% respondent. The respondents include a number of married, Single, divorced and widow. 49% respondents were married. Most of them have children along with them. The respondents have the education of Bachelor's, Master's, Professional or Doctorate degrees. 72.5% respondents hold a master's degree.

Measures and Scales Used

All study variables were measured at different likert scale. Occupational Stress, Job Performance and Supervisor’s Support were measured at a scale of 1-5. Social Support was measured at 1-7 likert scale.

Occupational Stress

This variable was measured using a 16 item scales of Caplan, R.D., Cobb, S., French, J.R.P., Jr., Harrison, R.V. and Pinneau, S.R. (1975). Job Demands and Worker Health, HEW Publication No. (NIOSH), pp. 75-160. The scale ranges from 1-5 describing the work situation and environment of the respondents. One sample item of the scale is “There is a difference of opinion among the members of my department”. The cronbach’s alpha reliability of the scale was 0.665 considered to be an reliable measure.

Job Performance

Job performance was measured using a 17 item scales of Cammann, C., Fichman, M., Jenkins, D., & Klesh, J. (1979). The Michigan Organizational Assessment Questionnaire. Unpublished manuscript, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor. The scale ranges from 1-5, describes how often have the respondent done each of the item on your present job. Scale of 1 = Never, 2 = Once or twice, 3 = Once or twice per month, 4 = Once or twice per week and 5 = Every day. One sample item of the scale is “Stayed home from work and said you were sick when you weren’t”. The cronbach’s alpha reliability of the scale was 0.938.

Social Support

Social support was measured by a 25 item scale of Weinert, C. (1987). A social support measure: PRQ85. *Nursing Research*, 36, 273-277. Scale ranges from 1-7 describing about the respondents personal opinions regarding their social relations. Scale of 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Somewhat Disagree, 4 = Neutral, 5 = Somewhat Agree, 6 = Agree and 7 = Strongly Agree. One sample item of the scale is “I spend time with others who have the same interests that I do”. The cronbach’s alpha reliability of the scale was 0.810.

Supervisor’s Support

Supervisor’s support was measured through a 7 item scale of McCreary, D. R., and Thompson M. M. (2006). Development of two reliable and valid measures of stressors in policing: The operational and organizational police stress questionnaires. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 13(4), 494-518. Scale ranges from 1-5 indicating the support of supervisor within the organization of respondent. Scale of 1 = Strongly Disagree leads towards 5 = Strongly Agree. One sample item of the scale is “My supervisor gives me credit for things I do well”. The cronbach’s alpha reliability of the scale was 0.742.

Control Variables

Table 1

ONE-WAY ANOVA

	F	p
Gender	7.480	.007
Age	13.557	.000
Marital Status	18.991	.000
No. of Children	4.773	.003
Education	2.225	.067

We use gender, age, marital status and no. of children as control variables as their probable significant direct effect on DV (Job Performance). A one-way ANOVA comparing job performance and occupational stress across gender, age, marital status, no. of children and education revealed that there were significant differences in occupational stress and job performance across organizations due to such demographic factors as gender (F =

7.480, $p < .05$), age ($F = 13.557, p < .05$), marital status ($F = 18.991, p < .05$) and no. of children ($F = 4.773, p < .05$). Education is not considered as a control variable due to its insignificant effect on such relationship.

Results

Descriptive, reliability, correlation and regression analysis

Table 2 present descriptive statistics, bivariate correlations, and reliability (coefficient) for all actions. Zero-order bivariate correlations were in the expected direction.

Table 2

Descriptive, reliability and correlation analysis

	Mean	SD	OS	SUS	SOS	JP
OS			(.665)			
Pearson Correlation	3.234	.389	1			
SUS				(.742)		
Pearson Correlation	3.420	.613	.038	1		
SOS					(.810)	
Pearson Correlation	5.027	.681	.048	.265**	1	
JP						(.938)
Pearson Correlation	1.738	.810	-.004	-.118	-.141*	1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Values in () shows the cronbech alpha reliability of the scale.

Regression Analysis

We apply multiple linear regression analysis to examine all main effect hypotheses (Hypothesis 1, 2 and 3). We entered gender, age, marital status and no. of children in the first step as control variables, followed by all independent and moderating variables. Table 2 (Step 2) shows the results for the main effects of OS and JP on the outcomes. JP was negatively related to OS ($\beta = 0.090, p < .001$) and positively related to Supervisor’s support ($\beta = .010, p < .001$) and Social Support ($\beta = .303, p < .05$). These results supported Hypothesis 1, 2 and 3.

Table 3

Regression Analysis

	B	JP R Square	Change in R Square
Step 1			
Control Variables			
Gender		.161	.161
Age			
Marital Status			
No. of children			
Step 2			
OS	-.090	.211	.049
SuS	.010		
SoS	.303		
Step 3			
OSxSuS	.202	.231	.020
OCxSoS	.363		

Moderating Influence of Supervisor's and Social Support

We apply moderated multiple regression analysis (Cohen, Cohen, West, & Aiken, 2003) to test Hypothesis 4 and 5. We entered the control variables at first step, then the independent and moderator variables in next step. We entered the interaction terms of the independent and moderator variables at the third step, which will confirm the moderation if significant.

Results available in Table 3 (Step 3) show that, controlling for the effects of OS, SuS and SoS, the interaction term of OS × SuS was significant for Job Performance ($\beta = 0.202, p < .05; \Delta R^2 = .02, p < .05$) and interaction term of OS × SoS was also significant ($\beta = 0.363, p < .001; \Delta R^2 = .02, p < .001$).

We construct the important interactions terms to check the high and low values moderation on the graph. The graph of such significant interactions terms are shown in Figures 1 and 2. Figure 1 shows that, the relationship of Occupational Stress and Job Performance weakens in the presence of Supervisor's Support.

Figure 1: Effect of Supervisor's Support on Job Performance

Figure shows the plot of the significant interaction for job performance. The slope for low and high Occupational Stress is significantly affected by the moderator and the slope is more steeper which means that in the existence of Supervisor's Support the employees can better perform their job duties and assignments and can better cope with the stress. The results supported Hypothesis 4 for Occupational Stress and Job performance being affected by the Supervisor's Support.

Figure 2: Effect of Social Support on Job Performance

Figure 2 shows the plot of slope for Occupational stress and job performance which is moderated by Social Support. The results supported Hypothesis 5 for Occupational Stress and Job Performance being affected by Social Support.

Conclusions and implications

Practical implications

The study can be useful for the managers to cope up with the employees facing stress. Supervisors can relate certain factors to effect job performance. They can also find the reasons of poor performance by the employees, whether such performance is due to the organizational factors or due to their personal life issues. Managers, associates and personal relations of the employees can play a better role for improved productivity and performance of the employees and can make them enable to perform better in the society and for the organization.

Limitations and direction for future study

The study is based on certain limitations like convenience sampling technique was used for collection of data. Sample size was comparatively small and collected from a small sector. Cross sectional design was used which create a common method bias.

Future researchers can use probability sampling technique for more accurate findings and results. They can also increase the sample size; can also study these variables with reference to a specific industry. The relationship of Occupational stress and job performance can also be moderated or mediated with other variables like coping style of the individual, personality, background, culture etc.

Discussion

Empirical evidences shows that most of our hypotheses, which were proposed for study, are supported. Occupational stress is found to be negatively affecting job performance of an employee which is the acceptance of our H1 which was related to the negative and significant effect of occupational stress on job performance.

Social support is found to be positively affecting job performance that is the reason for accepting our H2 which shows the employees supported socially can positively perform their job's functions and duties.

Supervisors support is positively and significantly found to effect job performance that support our H3 that employees can perform better if they are supported by their supervisors.

The moderated regression and graphs presents that the two factors i.e. Social Support and Supervisors Support are being affecting the relationship of Occupational Stress and Job Performance in a positive way. The person who is being supported socially and supervisory can better perform for the organization. So, our H4 and H5 also find empirical evidences to be supported.

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